

ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CFRP BOSSES IN COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS CONSIDERING DIFFERENT STIFFNESS DISTRIBUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Reducing the weight of pressure vessels is a key objective in different sectors like automotive or aerospace. This can be achieved by replacing Type III and IV pressure vessels through Type V design. Nonetheless, Type V pressure vessels still use metallic bosses as an interface to surrounding structures. These metallic bosses lower the performance of the Type V design due to its mass and mechanical and thermal properties. This study investigates the feasibility of CFRP bosses using different stiffness distributions by means of finite element analysis. Different materials are investigated to demonstrate the potential of these structures. The weight benefit as well as the mechanical performance is compared to metallic bosses.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for launch capabilities results in a high number of new players in the aerospace sector. Besides topics like reusability of launcher architectures, one aspect for being successful is to reduce the mass of the launcher architectures. [1]

In this research field, when it comes to the pressure vessel (PV) design, various studies focus on improving the performance of the PV by changing from a Type III to Type V design. By this, the metallic liner is replaced by the exclusive use of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). This results in an estimated mass benefit of composite PVs (CPV) of up to approximately 55 % [2]. While this is an advantageous step towards lower structural mass, it also imposes design challenges, especially for the storage of cryogenic fluids. In the space sector, media such as liquid oxygen (LOx) or liquid hydrogen (LH2) are stored at cryogenic temperatures such as 77K for LOx and 20K for LH2. During the filling process of the PVs, the structure is cooled down starting from room temperature (RT) to the cryogenic service temperature. From a design perspective, this results in high thermal induced residual stresses in joining areas between different materials because of their differing coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE). State of art, type III as well as Type V designs still rely on metallic bosses as interface to surrounding structures and pipings. To reduce these thermal stresses, it is beneficial to replace the metallic bosses by CFRP material design concepts. In addition to the reduced thermal mismatch between the design materials, CFRP structures are also capable of providing higher specific strengths compared to special alloys such as Invar36. Invar36 is frequently used as a design solution to minimise the CTE difference between the metallic component and the CFRP overwrap of the PV because of its low CTE [3]. While the CTE mismatch is reduced, Invar36 has a high density of 8.1 g/cm³ which lowers the structural performance [4]. Another disadvantage is the low strength at room temperature [5].

Concluding, the introduction of CFRP bosses leads to the following advantages:

- reduced mismatch of CTE between boss and laminate of the CPV
- increased specific strength of the CFRP boss based on the used CFRP material
- reduced density of the CFRP boss

These advantages make the development of CFRP bosses interesting for the future use in the aerospace sector. There are some studies, which highlight the potential described above of the CFRP bosses. *Whitehead et al.* integrated a CFRP boss manufactured by hand layup into a CPV to achieve weight reduction of the pressure vessel. A CFRP boss concept manufactured by resin infusion is shown by *Scherer et al.* [6]. Here, CFRP preforms are used to increase the performance of the boss structure. Another study showed that recycled material can be implemented into CFRP boss parts as core material, related to a sandwich structure design by *Korff et al.* [7]. The use of SMC bosses in an integrated Type V CPV design was demonstrated in a previous study by *Rehs et al.* [8]. Here, the performance of an SMC boss was compared to the Aluminum design in a Type V concept. Similar results for burst pressure performance as well as helium leak behaviour was demonstrated on part level. Furthermore, the manufacturing and integration of prepreg bosses on a 20L CPV was demonstrated. A weight saving of up to 57% in comparison to a steel boss is demonstrated by changing the boss material without considering the geometry. [8]

In this study, the performance increase of the CFRP bosses is assessed by the use of finite element (FE) analysis. Different materials and stiffness distributions of the CFRP boss structures are analysed based on the CFRP preform.

2 MATERIAL DEFINITION AND ANALYSIS MODEL

In this section, the material and analysis model are described. Five different materials are compared to highlight the potential of CFRP boss parts. The analysis focuses on the advantages which come with the material parameters as well as the manufacturing induced advantages.

2.1 Material Definition

Different materials can be used for the manufacturing of boss structures. Currently, state of the art boss structures are manufactured by metals such as Aluminum or Invar36. Replacing these structures by CFRP can be done using different CFRP preforms like fabrics, Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC), unidirectional (UD) prepregs or spiral ribbon.

This study focuses on the analysis of SMC and twill and UD prepregs, compared to the metal design of Aluminum 6082 and Invar36 to highlight the benefits of the CFRP structure.

Therefore, the design parameters such as strength, stiffness, density and CTE for the different materials are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Material data for metal and CFRP materials [4, 9-13]

Metal Materials			
Parameter		Al	Invar36
E	[MPa]	70714	143000
R_{yield}	[MPa]	298.3	270
CTE	[$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	23.5	1.3
ρ	[g/cm^3]	2.7	8.1

CFRP Materials				
Parameter		SMC	Twill Prepreg	UD Prepreg
E_f	[MPa]	25000	68000	164000
R_f	[MPa]	300	1050	2724
CTE	[$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	10	3.62	-0.5 – 12.5
ρ	[g/cm^3]	1.9	1.47	1.57

For the design of light structures different parameters are of interest, shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Material comparisons. (a) Strength to Density Ratio at RT, (b) Strength to Stiffness Ratio at RT, (c) CTE at RT

First, the strength to stiffness ratio is shown in Figure 1 (a), which is important for the lightweight potential. It can be seen, that Invar36 shows the lowest strength to density ratio and Prepreg material shows the highest strength. For the metal materials, the yield strength was chosen as strength value as typical design approaches follow a no yield design under service conditions. For the CFRP materials, the strength describes the stress at fiber failure.

Second, the design of boss structures is driven by a bending load in the boss runout. This is why a high strength to stiffness ratio is beneficial, shown in Figure 1 (b). Due to the inner pressure loading the CPV undergoes a deformation which is mainly driven by the CFRP laminate stiffness distribution. As the boss is attached to the overwrap, it undergoes this deformation as well. This deformation yields to bending in the runout. Therefore, a high strength to stiffness value of the design material is beneficial for the lightweight potential. It can be seen in Figure 1 (b) that CFRP materials offer higher values compared to the metal materials. This is also in accordance with experimental results observed in [8] on part level.

Third, for the use in cryogenic temperatures, the CTE is of interest, shown in Figure 1 (c). Here, a low CTE is proven to be beneficial. An optimal boss design would show the same CTE compared to the CFRP overwrap in the joining area. Due to the winding process and changing fiber angles in the boss region, the prediction of the CTE of the overwrap remains difficult and should be addressed in future studies. Based on the state of the art, where Invar36 proves to be a design solution it can be concluded that Invar36 and Prepreg Materials are of high interest, while SMC offers way better characteristics compared to Aluminum.

Concluding, the use of CFRP Materials for boss design proves to be a promising approach within Type V CPV design for further increasing the CPV performance index due to the following advantages:

- CFRP shows high R/ρ values especially compared to Invar36
- CFRP shows high R/E values especially compared to Invar36
- CFRP shows lower CTE values especially compared to Aluminum

2.2 Finite Element Model

A finite element (FE) model is used to predict the mechanical responses for the loading situation of the CPV including different boss designs and materials based on section 2.1.

The *Abaqus* FE-model is generated on basis of a winding simulation performed with the winding software *uChain* by *MeFeX GmbH*. The model consists of two parts, the boss part and the CFRP laminate. The CPV laminate is composed of 22 layers, containing helical and hoop layers. The design of the boss was chosen to withstand an inner pressure loading of 400 bar using Invar36 as design material. The loading is applied as inner pressure loading on the boss and the CFRP laminate inner surface as well as an axial force on a Reference Point (RP) to account for the cover loading. The load of the RP is transferred using a coupling to the boss structure. The analysis uses an axisymmetric approach using CAX3/4 element formulation with an element size of 0.75 mm. A symmetric boundary condition is used in the center of the CPV constraining the axial deformation. Second, a boundary condition is used at the RP.

Figure 2 shows boss part as well as the CFRP laminate of the CPV. The loading can be seen on the inner surface as well as the reference point.

Figure 2: FE-model showing the two parts (boss and CPV laminate) as well as the loading and boundary conditions of the axisymmetric model.

Based on the shown design and FE model, different analyses are performed including geometric variations of the boss design as well as the analyses of different boss materials.

2.3 Boss manufacturing

As described before, different materials for CFRP are considered in this study: SMC and Prepreg. Based on this, the manufacturing process differs between these two materials.

In general, the CFRP boss consists of two parts. The CFRP main body and a metallic insert, which allows for connection of the CPV to pipes via standard pressure fitting [8]. The metallic insert is designed to be as small as possible to reduce weight and also have less absolute difference of thermal expansion between the parts. It is bonded to the CFRP main body in an extra step after the CFRP part is manufactured.

To use the advantages of a CFRP boss mentioned before, the manufacturing process has to be considered during the design of the boss. The two manufacturing methods are SMC compression molding and prepreg autoclave manufacturing.

In the SMC process, a preform that contains long fiber and resin is inserted in a two part heated mold. The mold is closed with a defined force to apply pressure. The viscosity of the resin decreases and can flow through the mold to fill the whole cavity and moving the fibers with it. In this process, relatively complex parts can be manufactured with short cycle times and minimal rework needed. Therefore, the process is well suited for high scale manufacturing. Another advantage of using this process for CFRP bosses is the freedom in the part geometry. The outer edge of the boss can be made thin to reduce stiffness gradients in the CPV. As the fibers in the preform have a random orientation the mechanical properties of the part will be quasi isotropic in in-plane direction.

The second manufacturing process considered for the CFRP boss is prepreg autoclave manufacturing. A positive mold which represents the underside of the boss is machined and CFRP prepreg is laid on it in multiple layers. Unidirectional and fabric material is used. The CFRP is cured inside an autoclave to apply pressure for compaction and good laminate quality. After curing the topside of the boss is milled to the exact contour as this cannot be achieved with the layup process alone. Advantages of this process are tailoring of the fiber directions to the loads in the boss and the use of endless fibers compared to isotropic materials resulting in high-strength parts. As a result, the boss can be made thinner and lighter with this manufacturing method.

Figure 3: CFRP Boss demonstrator manufactured from twill and UD prepreg. [8]

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the loading and stress analysis based on Invar36 material design. Following this analysis results, different boss adaptations including geometric variations and material variations are presented.

3.1 Loading and stress analysis of the Invar36 boss design and its limitations

The detailed design procedure of the boss, which undergoes the deformation behaviour of the CFRP laminate is not focus of this study. Rather, on the basis of the shown design, different variations are analysed to highlight the mentioned potential of replacing metal bosses through CFRP design. The design is chosen for an operating CPV inner pressure of 400 bar.

For experimental validation of the shown design, the Invar36 boss with the CPV laminate was pressurized up to 500 bar using a hydrostatic pressure test bench. The design showed no failure of the boss structure.

All following results are derived at the operating pressure of 400 bar.

Figure 4 (a) shows the von Mises stress distribution of the Invar36 boss. The boss undergoes an axial displacement due to the CFRP overwrap deformation behaviour. For simplicity, the CFRP laminate is not shown in Figure 4. The volume towards the interface to the CFRP laminate is in a high tensile stress state. This is because of the bending loading situation triggered by the axial displacement of the CPV. As a result, the material towards the interface is loaded under tensile stresses, while the lower material is not highly loaded due to the presence of compressive stresses due to the bending. Reducing this area of the part is not advisable, due to the failure mode of shear out and further increasing the yielding tendency. If the part thickness becomes too low, the boss part can fail in the area which is highlighted in

Figure 4 (a). Due to the inner pressure loading, there are also stress components in the circumferential direction shown by the stress vectors of the maximum principal stresses in Figure 4 (b). Concluding, the boss stress state is complex due to the different aspects of the loading and there are different aspects to be considered in the optimization of the boss using layered structures.

Figure 4: (a) Von Mises stress distribution of the Invar36 boss at 400 bar inner pressure loading. Stresses depicted in grey are above the $R_{p0.2}$ limit for Invar36. (b) Maximum principal stress distribution shown in vectors.

The high loading in the ending section of the boss (yielding area) can be reduced by increasing the thickness of this runout. While this accounts true for the boss, the CFRP laminate has to be also considered. This poses a design challenge. On the one side, the runout should be as thick as possible due to possible yielding failure in the boss runout. On the other side, the runout should be as thin as possible due to the presence of the stiffness jump in the interface between the boss and the CFRP laminate.

This design challenge is analysed in Figure 5. For this study, the overall boss geometry is kept similar, only the runout thickness of the boss is changed from 0.25 mm to 1.00 mm. By this, the global stiffness change of the runout variation for the CPV system is kept to a minimum. For analysis, the mean yield von Mises stress in the runout was extracted. Therefore, the von Mises stress was evaluated on the integration points in the runout volume, shown in red in Figure 5. The fiber stresses of layer 1 was derived directly in the interface boss to CFRP laminate (Layer 1 bottom) and the interface between Layer 1 and Layer 2 (Layer 1 top).

Figure 5 Fiber stress in the top and bottom of layer 1 at the location of the runout end of the boss as well as the yield stress in the runout end (shown in red) of the metal boss for an inner pressure loading of 400 bar in variation of the runout thickness end.

It must be noted, that the results shown in Figure 5 represent general design trends. The quantitative values may be affected by numerical singularities in the joining area of the boss and the CFPR overwrap. This is also a challenge of the boss interface and needs to be addressed in future research.

Figure 5 shows that the overall yield stress in the runout reduces with increasing runout thickness. Increasing the runout thickness therefore reduces the risk of yield induced failure as the runout area shows lower overall loading. The stresses for the fiber direction in Layer 1 of the CPV laminate show that the increase in runout thickness causes an increase in loading especially in the bottom of Layer 1. This joining area between boss and CPV laminate is a very important interface for functional requirements such as leakage, especially in Type V designs. This is why these trends shown in Figure 5 are critical.

The effect of increasing fiber stresses with increasing runout thickness is not present towards the upper layers of the laminate. The fiber stresses slightly decrease in the interface of Layer 1 and 2 which is due to the different deformation behaviour caused by the stiffness change of the boss runout.

A result of Figure 5 is that the engineer always has to choose between a low loading with regard to yielding of the boss or a lower loading of the CFRP layers in the laminate. The decrease in runout thickness is limited by the need to prevent the metallic bosses from yield failure. This is why the change of material to CFPR can be promising due to the material properties discussed in section 2.1.

Therefore, the next section discusses the change of boss material and highlights the possible benefits.

3.2 Analysis of different boss materials

Based on the results of the Invar36 boss, the use of Aluminum, SMC and prepreg materials is discussed. The design comparison between Invar36, Aluminum and SMC is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Boss Design Material Comparison: (a) Invar36 design, (b) Aluminum design, (c) SMC design. Shown is the von Mises stresses for (a) and (b) with $R_{p0,2}$ as limit, for (c) the maximum principal stresses are displayed with the failure stress of SMC as limit.

For Aluminum, the strength to density and strength to stiffness ratio is better compared to Invar36. Consequently, the yield behaviour at the same inner pressure is reduced compared to the Invar36 design, which can be seen in the von Mises stresses in Figure 6. Also, the overall stiffness is reduced, resulting in a less pronounced stiffness jump at the boss end. Both favours the Aluminum design. As a design adaptation, the thickness could be reduced resulting in lower mass not only due to the lower density but also due to the reduced need of metal material.

These benefits are limited to room temperature applications, as the CTE mismatch to the CFRP laminate is too high for the use in cryogenic conditions.

Similar results are observed for the SMC boss design. SMC offers even better strength to stiffness and strength to density values compared to Aluminum. The advantages of the Aluminum design are therefore also applicable to the SMC design. Lower density and higher strength can further decrease the weight of a SMC boss compared to Aluminum. In addition, the CTE is reduced compared to Aluminum. Further research needs to investigate until which temperatures SMC can be used in low temperature applications. Both, SMC and Aluminum also offer a significant weight decrease compared to the Invar36 design.

Based on the results discussed, a prepreg boss offers the unique chance to tailor the laminate more to the loading situation compared to isotropic materials. Above, SMC was treated as isotropic, as a simplification. Future research could also investigate the in- and out-of-plane stiffness distribution of SMC with regard to the mechanical and thermal behaviour of the CPV.

Reviewing Figure 4, the runout area should be reinforced with prepreg in fiber direction located towards the bending stresses. Like a sandwich design, fibers can be applied to the inner and outer contour and the middle section can be filled with twill prepreg, or even lower density materials as discussed in [7]. Towards the fluid adapters a high circumferential loading is observed in Figure 4. This loading can be taken up best by fibers located in circumferential direction (here called 90°).

A demonstration of this design procedure is shown in Figure 7. The layup of the prepreg boss is shown in Figure 7 (a). The SMC section in the upper part is a simplification for the analysis and not of relevance for the loading situation and offers no major influence on the deformation behavior and is therefore not further discussed.

Compared to the Invar36 design, the overall thickness is reduced, as prepreg offers higher strength compared to SMC. The results in Figure 6 (c) show that SMC already provides stresses below the strength of SMC. As a consequence, the loading of a boss with identical geometry will be even lower. That is why for this analysis, the overall thickness of the boss was lowered.

Figure 7 (b) shows the result of this analysis. Here, the maximum principal stresses are shown at 400 bar inner pressure. As a strength limit, the twill strength of 1050 MPa is chosen. As the UD strength is higher, see Table 1, this approach is conservative.

Figure 7: CFRP Prepreg Boss: (a) Fiber distribution (0° following the boss contour, 90° in Z direction), (b) Maximum principal stresses with Twill Prepreg Strength as limit.

It can be concluded that the loading situation is lower compared to Invar36 design even with the lower part thickness regarding the twill strength. Also, the peak stress within the CPV laminate is reduced. Because of the use of CFRP material, the design challenge is shown in Figure 5 resolved. Low runout thicknesses are possible to the use of CFRP material with a suitable fiber orientation. This also causes the lower peak stress of the laminate at the bottom of layer 1. Additionally, the shear out failure mode can be resolved by the correct use of fiber orientation.

Comparing the volume of the two boss configurations, a volume reduction of 33% is observed for the CFRP boss. Taking the density into account, this adds up to a weight reduction of 87%. This lowers the mass from 2,29 kg per boss for the Invar36 boss to only 295 g for the CFRP bosses. Considering the neglected adapter for fluid adaption, which will lower the mass benefit, this still is a remarkable result, especially as the design can be further optimized considering the stress distribution in Figure 7 (b). Related to the overall tank mass, this would be a mass decrease of 28% for the whole CPV.

This emphasizes the structural benefit which is present in the concept of replacing Invar36 bosses through CFRP bosses. As the CTE of Twill and UD prepreg is also low, cryogenic temperatures are also in scope of the design solution. The CFRP boss offers lower mass and higher strengths compared to Invar36 and also a low CTE.

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Summary

In conclusion, this study analyses and discusses the benefits of CFRP boss materials based on a tested CPV with Invar36 bosses.

First, a material comparison highlights a material selection to replace Invar36 as design material. The benefits of these materials are discussed and summarized in this study. Consequently, a FE-model is set up to investigate and evaluate the loading situation of the baseline boss material Invar36. A variation of the runout geometry is performed to show the design challenge using Invar36 as design material. Based on this, different materials for boss manufacturing are analysed. The results show that Aluminum and SMC show advantages over the Invar36 boss at room temperature. The use of prepreg materials such as UD and twill further increase these advantages. Due to the low CTE of prepreg CFRP bosses they can be also interesting in cryogenic temperatures.

Based on the results it can be concluded that the use of CFRP bosses offer a high potential for decreasing the weight of CPVs. Compared to the weight saving of changing from Type III or IV designs to Type V designs, this change of boss material should also be considered.

In addition to the weight savings of the boss itself, there is also a positive impact on the CPV laminate. The stiffness jump in the joining area of the boss to the CPV laminate can be tailored. Especially with the use of layered structures such as Twill and UD prepreg, the stiffness distribution can be adjusted to the predicted deformation behaviour of the tank system containing the boss and the CPV laminate. This has a direct impact on the design process of the CPV laminate which is expected to further decrease the system mass as helical layers, which are needed to control yielding in the boss region for metallic designs are less likely to be needed in case of a CFRP boss. Both, the lower CFRP boss weight and the lower CPV laminate weight are positive for the performance of the CPV system.

4.2 Future research

Future studies can investigate the detailed tailoring of the layered CFRP boss structure to the deformation behaviour of the CPV coupled to the CPV laminate deformation. This interaction of both parts will result in a lower overall CPV mass which can then be evaluated in an experimental campaign. A more detailed analysis of the SMC boss stiffness distribution increases the accuracy of the analysis.

Another aspect of future research is to evaluate the use of SMC in low temperature applications. It needs to be evaluated if the CTE mismatch between the CPV laminate and the SMC boss is sufficiently low enough for the use of SMC bosses at low temperatures. Detailed analysis of the deformation behaviour of the CPV laminate and the boss in a joined state are needed to evaluate this.

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